

Stellar population gradients of SAMI central galaxies

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Massive galaxies at $z \sim 2$ are already found to be quiescent, but compact, with an effective radius (R_e) half of the size of galaxies of similar mass in the local universe [e.g., 1, 2, 3]. Hydrodynamical-zoom cosmological simulations found that massive galaxies likely form in a two-phase formation scenario [e.g., 4]. During the first phase, at high redshift, they grow by a rapid episode of in-situ star formation, resulting in compact massive systems. The initial stellar metallicity gradient is set by the initial episode of star formation, with the metallicity decreasing outward in the galaxy [5, 6]. From this process, we would expect steep, negative metallicity gradients and flat age radial profiles. After $z \approx 2$, these massive compact galaxies ($\log_{10}(M_*/M_\odot) > 10.5$) are predicted to be quiescent and grow mostly by accreting mass through galaxy interactions that add stars to their outskirts [4, 7, 8].

Integral field spectroscopy enables the mapping of stellar populations and kinematics across individual galaxies, rather than obtaining parameters from only the centre or one axis of the galaxy as fibre or long-slit observations do. My first PhD research project focused on studying the stellar population profiles of massive passive galaxies in order to understand how massive galaxies evolve. In particular, the main goal of this work was to determine whether central galaxies have different stellar population properties when compared to similarly massive satellite galaxies. The stellar populations of galaxies provide a means by which to determine their evolutionary histories. The efficiency of star formation, gas fractions and mergers leave imprints in the radial distributions of these populations. We studied the stellar population (age, metallicity, and $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$) radial profiles of passive galaxies in the SAMI Galaxy Survey.

Galaxy sample

The Sydney-AAO Multi-object Integral field spectrograph (SAMI) Galaxy Survey is a large, optical Integral Field Spectroscopy [9] survey of low-redshift ($0.04 < z < 0.095$) galaxies covering a broad range in stellar mass, $7 < \log_{10}(M_*/M_\odot) < 12$, morphology and environment. The sample, with ≈ 3000 galaxies, is selected from the Galaxy and Mass Assembly Survey (GAMA survey; [10]) regions (group galaxies), as well as eight additional clusters to probe higher-density environments [11].

Our sample consists of 533 passive galaxies with reliable measurements for metallicity and age in at least 3 annular apertures (96 central galaxies and 437 satellite galaxies) and 332 galaxies with reliable measurements for $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$ in at least three annular apertures (79 centrals and 253 satellites). We focus on the passive central galaxies to ensure a like-to-like comparison in determining how their central and satellite status affects their stellar population gradients.

Figure 1: Metallicity gradients as a function of stellar mass. Individual gradients are shown in purple for central galaxies (left panel) and blue for satellites (middle panel) and the median value in bins of stellar mass in bold. The right panel shows the median gradient values for each mass bin in the two environments. Metallicity gradients are negative and shallow, for both central and satellite galaxies.

Figure 2: Age gradients as a function of stellar mass. All point types are as per Figure 1. Age gradients are generally positive and shallow for both central and satellite galaxies.

Figure 3: $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$ gradients as a function of stellar mass. All point types are as per Figure 1. $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$ gradients are consistent with zero for both central and satellite galaxies. We find a weak trend of the gradients with stellar mass.

Results

For the whole sample, we find negative metallicity radial gradients, which show evidence of becoming shallower with increasing stellar mass (Figure 1). The age and $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$ gradients are slightly positive and consistent with zero, respectively (Figure 2 and Figure 3). The $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$ gradients become more negative with increasing mass, while the age gradients do not show any significant trend with mass. We do not observe a significant difference between the stellar population gradients of central and satellite galaxies at fixed stellar mass. The mean age and $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$ gradients are consistent between central and satellite galaxies, within the uncertainties. The stellar population gradients of central and satellite galaxies show no difference as a function of halo mass.

The gradients we find are consistent with those predicted for galaxies formed in a two-phase process [7, 12].

In this scenario, galaxies first undergo a rapid formation phase during which 'in-situ' stars are formed within the galaxy. The more massive ETGs start forming stars at earlier epochs. The resulting galaxy is compact, with a steep negative metallicity gradient (with gradients ranging from $\Delta[Z/H]/\Delta \log(r/R_e) = -0.35$ to -1.0 ; [12]) and a positive age gradient (due to the presence of a younger stellar population in the center of the galaxy). More specifically, the metallicity and age gradients would naturally correlate with galaxy mass as star formation lasts longer in the center of more massive systems which have deeper central potential wells [e.g. 12], so that more massive galaxies would have younger and more metal-rich centers, more positive age gradients and more negative metallicity gradients.

After the star formation is quenched, a second phase of slower evolution is dominated by dissipationless mergers. In particular, galaxy interactions will either steepen or flatten the metallicity gradients: major dissipationless mergers tend to cause gradients to become shallower, as metal-rich stars from the centre of the galaxy are redistributed further out (e.g., [12, 13]) and minor dissipationless mergers lead to steeper negative metallicity gradients, due to metal-poor stars being accreted in the outer regions from lower mass galaxies (e.g., [14]).

Central galaxies, due to their privileged position in the center of the potential well, are expected to experience a greater number of galaxy interactions compared to satellite galaxies. In this scenario, simulations predict flat or slightly positive age gradients, due to old stars being added in the outer regions (at radii $> 2R_e$; [14]), and $[\alpha/Fe]$ profiles are expected to be flat as a result of massive early-type galaxies assembling via mergers with low-mass systems [15]. These predictions are in agreement with our findings: the metallicity gradients we find are shallower than those predicted by a monolithic col-

lapse (ranging from $\Delta[Z/H]/\Delta \log(r/R_e) = -0.5$ [16] to $\Delta[Z/H]/\Delta \log(r/R_e) = -1.0$ [12]), hinting to a flattening of the gradients due to mergers. The age gradients are slightly positive (with central stars having younger ages than stars in the outskirts) and generally flat $[\alpha/Fe]$ gradients. However, since evidence of minor later accretions are expected at radii $> 1.5-2R_e$ and the majority of the radial profiles for our central galaxies only extend to a maximum of $2R_e$, our results point to a similar evolution path for the inner regions of both central and satellite galaxies.

The fact that our metallicity gradients for central and satellite galaxies are consistent within the standard deviation suggests that the inner regions of central galaxies (up to $2R_e$) form in a similar fashion to similarly massive satellite galaxies. Moreover, the gradients for galaxies in high-mass halos show no trend with stellar mass. This seems to point to a similar evolution for galaxies in denser environments, regardless of their current position in the halo [17].

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